

CHARACTERISTICS OF HUMAN STRENGTH

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Abstract

the article is devoted to the specific characteristics of human potential, the content of such concepts as potential, capital, human potential, human capital, labor force, intellectual capital, human resources is also touched upon, the specific characteristics of human potential are revealed. human potential in relation to them.

Key words

potential, capital, human potential, human capital, labor force, intellectual capital, human resources, cultural capital, social capital.

In the Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020: "Three years ago we started a lot of work to raise the development of our country to a new level. Relying on the intellect, strength and potential of our people (our italics - K.D.), we are achieving initial, but extremely important and weighty results along this path. Now we must build on these gains and take even bolder and more ambitious steps. "Because the process of reforms and transformations in our country is entering a decisive phase, taking an irreversible turn." This issue does not leave the agenda over time. Perhaps its importance is increasing day by day. In his next address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan on December 20, 2022, the head of state also spoke about human potential: worthy life of people" means creation, reduction of poverty. Therefore, first of all, we will focus on supporting education, which is the largest investment for New Uzbekistan. It can be seen from them that the relevance of the problems associated with increasing human potential is increasing day by day.

Issues related to human potential are being studied by world scientists. But in this case, human capital, labor force, intellectual capital, human resources and its content are theoretically little studied by our scientists. Taking this into account, we

considered it an objective necessity to systematically consider the content of these concepts. Because the employment of the world's population in specialties, their scientific and professional potential directly depend on the professional areas of the population, the quality and effectiveness of education. Given this, a number of studies are being carried out in this direction. These include the studies of A. Abdurakhmanov, S. S. Gulomov, N. Arabov, M. M. Mukhammedov, M. K. Pardaev, G. M. Shodieva, O. M. Pardaeva, Sh. O. Kuvandikov, aimed at solution to these problems.

Clarification of the theoretical issues of human potential and capital is one of the most important problems. Because in modern economic literature the concept of human potential is called human capital, labor force, intellectual capital. If we analyze them theoretically, we can draw the following theoretical conclusions. To do this, first of all, let us turn to the explanation of the concepts of "authority" and "capital".

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the concept of "authority" is explained as follows. This word comes from the Arabic language and expresses the concepts of "(suitability; authority, dominance; full power) ability, talent." In connection with the use of this word, the word "competent" means "competent, of great ability; it is noted that it consists of "talented" concepts. So, the concept of potential is expressed in our fiction in a peculiar way. For example, one of the famous writers of the Uzbek people, Odil Yakubov, said: "God gave such a potential to this blessed breed, there is no knowledge in the field of medicine that he would not know." So, potential means a person with great abilities, knowledgeable and, accordingly, talented.

In the dictionary mentioned under this title, the concept of "capital" is explained as follows. This word is of German origin and has three interpretations.

1. From the point of view of the economy Wealth used for self-reproduction, bringing profit and income to its owner (securities, money, material property, etc.).

2. A large amount, a lot of money, wealth. Accumulation of capital in the hands of certain individuals.

3. It is said that someone has great wealth, value, important, important thing.

4. It seems that capital is not used at all in relation to a person and to all beings. Because of this, calling a potential person "human capital" is somewhat controversial .

The theory of "human capital" calculates the amount of investment directly in a person. It is appropriate to consider that this is not human capital, but investments aimed at increasing human potential. According to the current theory

of the concept of human capital, there is a notion that investment in people leads to economic growth. This is the wrong view. An investment in a person does not pay off directly.

No matter how much you invest in him, if he does not have the ability to mobilize himself, the skills to perform the relevant work, the knowledge, such a theory may not be justified.

Some countries certainly spend money to produce more highly educated people for their people. The sum of these expenses is 2.0 billion dollars. If so, then the value of human capital cannot be estimated. These funds are used to increase the level of skills and knowledge of human potential, more precisely, these are targeted investments. The amount of investment cannot be called human capital. Some theories use the term "human resources" instead of human capital. But this concept cannot be compared with human capital. It should be borne in mind that in the current conditions all resources are being sold, but human resources are not being sold, and it is difficult to determine their cost. Currently, employers are hiring employees. He does not buy it with money, but receives a salary for his work throughout his career. It is not the value of the worker that is saved, but part of the value created by his work. If a person is qualified, educated and experienced, he will bring great benefits to employers and society as a whole. This benefit is not human capital, but a product of human labor with high potential.

There is a unique theory of K. Mark about human capital, which he calls human capital "labor force" and attaches the importance of human capital to the strength of the worker. According to the theory of K. Markas, people in capitalist systems sell their labor power in exchange for income, i.e. wages. It is said that this sold labor force is human capital. There is one mistake here. The sold capital must pass from one person to another. But both the active worker and his potential, that is, abilities, remain with the worker himself. In this case, the sale process does not take place, and the entire potential remains embodied in the person himself. If human skills and abilities were capital, capital could be sold like other capitals. But there is no way to sell to a person. These theoretical views also show that it is correct to call it human potential and not human capital.

Many scientists have expressed their opinion about the theory of "human capital". In particular, according to the idea of Adam Smith, human capital was called "the acquired and useful abilities of all inhabitants or members of society." Smith theorizes that wage differentials depend on the ability of the workers doing the work and proposes that it be valued based on the relative ease or difficulty of the work they do.

It is worth noting that people (slaves) were sold during the time of slavery. Their price did not depend on his qualifications. If at that time people were called human capital, then the sale of people was stopped. Along with this came the end of the human capital market. Now, after the end of the sale of man, it is doubtful to call it capital. Therefore, the most correct interpretation, in our opinion, is the concept of "human potential".

In conclusion, it should be noted that, firstly, "human capital" does not fully express "human potential". Instead of human capital, it is correct to use the phrase "human potential".

Secondly, each person in the course of his activity creates something, performs work and provides services. In this case, a person is not for sale, but uses his potential and mobilizes himself. At the same time, a person does not sell himself, but only works.

Thirdly, due to the different potential of each person, the level of products they create, the work they perform, and the services they provide are also different. In this regard, the effectiveness of human potential is also different. Accordingly, he receives a salary from the employer. Wages are wages for work performed, not the cost of the worker.

Fourth, investment in education is now referred to as investment in "human capital". This investment is not in human capital, but in the growth of human potential. The higher the potential of a person, the more a person can create many quality things at the same time compared to a person without potential. It does not depend on the value of the so-called "human capital".

One of the important features and characteristics of the economy is getting more money by making money. To get something, you need to spend something. Those who claim to earn more will have to spend more. To make spending more efficient, funds given to workers should not only be for wages, but should also be used to encourage the development of the economy. This process, in turn, leads to the development of business management. At the same time, along with "human capital", it is necessary to expand the management of "human resources". Human resource theory, unlike human capital, is seen as a controlled entity. However, this may vary depending on the capacity of the resources. It also cannot be equated with human capital or human potential.

Human resources may include the totality of people capable of working in a society. From the point of view of the enterprise, it includes the employees employed in it. It is also natural that each of them has a different potential. But in terms of purpose, they all want to make a profit. To do this, the workers really have

to use their conscious abilities and their body (arms and legs). But their ability to do something differs in volume, time and quality, they are not the same. The level of this depends on the scientific and professional potential of each person.

Human potential is used on the basis of a contract. To do this, workers aim for a standard wage and employers aim for the net profit of the process. In other words, workers spend their mental and physical labor, while maintaining their labor potential, that is, the labor force. They will need to work effectively so that the result of this work is at a high level. This requires that its potential be high. The employer's salary expenses must not exceed his income. Otherwise, the use of human capital will end in failure. This, of course, does not allow for sustainable development and efficiency.

Conclusions and offers. In short, human potential is a unique concept that is distinct from human capital, labor force, intellectual capital, human resources, cultural capital and social capital.

First, if we compare human potential with the usual labor force, then there are currently temporary unemployed. They prefer to temporarily work for someone so as not to waste their time in vain. Thus, they will have a daily income. Such people do not sell their labor force, but do the assigned work and bring it to the end.

Second, in this process, they enter into mutually beneficial temporary contracts with employers to use their skills in exchange for wages. Employers create products using the labor of employees. This product is for sale. Similarly, farmers and other entrepreneurs sell their crops. In this sale, human potential is not sold as if it were capital.

Thirdly, it should be noted that a person was sold only during slavery. It could only be valued as human capital as a worker. Because they have become the property of people. Whoever invested them owned it and served it. To date, the use of the concept of human capital theoretically does not fully express its content. Therefore, it is advisable to use the concept of human potential.

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